

Diversity and Modern Politics

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Introduction

Over the years, the concept of diversity has emerged to be an issue of concern in terms of political challenges across the globe. In this regard, it has been widely argued by the political thinkers that it typically stems from a number of intricate factors. The most prominent of these factors is considered to be globalization (Clarke 2008). Moreover, it has also been observed that there is a stark difference between the ancient and modern political theories that study the problems of diversity. The present study aims to highlight the aspects of modern approach to diversity with specific focus on the work of three renowned political thinkers.

Modern Approach to Diversity

In the context of modern approach, it has been observed that the society seems wary of embracing the concept of diversity. In the contemporary times, there is an existence of diversity not only in culture, but also in the values and traditions between various groups of the community. Therefore, there is an increasing need to devise effective ways for dealing with the challenges and threats posed by diversity (Clarke 2008). In addition to this, it is critical that the problems viewed by the modern aspect of diversity are resolved so that the advancement of marginalized groups may be enhanced. According to the modern approach, the social reformism is considered to be associated with the modern liberalism (Baumeister 2007). In this regard, it is believed that the concepts of universal citizenship as well as formal equality are not enough for formulating the issues of marginalization.

Diversity as an Issue for Modern Political Life

A number of political thinkers believe that diversity is a major issue of concern for the modern society. According to Habermas, the challenges that cultural diversity as well as

pluralism pose in the modern life cannot be efficiently resolved by a systematic approach, which emphasizes exclusively on the aspects of political legitimacy. Therefore, in relation to the constitutional patriotism, various modern states have to make significant efforts for building a uniform and central political identity (Clarke 2008). Moreover, in view of another scholar, Karl Polanyi, it has been argued that it is critical for the modern society to work for the aspects that ensure a peaceful coexistence of diverse social, political, and economic formations. Through this, the growing interdependence of the entire world in relation to diversity may be addressed. Finally, Michel Foucault asserted that in order to understand the varying nature of diversity in the modern world, it is critical to analyze the intersection of knowledge and power (Baumeister 2007). Through this, diversity normalization may be achieved up to some extent.

Resolution of Differences between the Groups

In the modern context, the conflicts between the groups on the basis of diversity are considered to be largely associated to the homogenization of assumptions. In this regard, the policies associated to assimilation are considered to be illegitimate at national and international levels (Baumeister 2007). Moreover, the pluralistic responses of the policy have gained momentum in regard to the affirmative programs for the protection of minority.

Benefits of Diversity

Some of the political thinkers are of the opinion that diversity is also beneficial in terms of the aspects that people from various backgrounds do not work alike (Clarke 2008). Therefore, there will be versatility in the traditions and ideas.

Conclusion

Diversity is viewed as a potential challenge by the political thinkers for the modern society. However, the differences between the concepts of various groups may effectively serve as a means to promote versatility and adaptability in the society.

References

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